

require an average of 0.8 weeding (mean of 8 d/ha) the first year and 1.6 weedings (17 d/ha) the next compared with chume land at 2.3 weedings (21 d/ha). Fifty-four percent of farmers sprayed insecticide for the large plant-sucking insect *petilla* (*Tibraca limbativentris*) or seed bugs. Some farmers reported losses to *petilla* of 50-80%.

Rice is harvested panicle-by-panicle with a hand knife, and threshing is done by foot. Rice is not winnowed. Yields

reported from the past two seasons averaged 0.8 t/ha. The highest yield any farmer obtained was 3.7 t/ha.

All of the farmers indicated weeds and lack of fertility to be their most important constraints, followed by *petilla* (80% of respondents). Other problems were mentioned by less than 27% of the farmers.

Other insect pests are grasshoppers and spittle bug (*Zulia* sp.). Common diseases are both leaf and neck blast,

brown leaf spot, narrow brown spot, and leaf scald. Blast is the most important of these, but it does not cause yield loss every year.

Because of the high labor input involved in slash-and-burn rice culture and stagnated yields, rainfed puddled rice culture might be an alternative in this high-rainfall area. ■

Yield ability and net return of rice-based cropping sequences under different water regimes in Bihar, India

U. K. Prasad, T. N. Prasad, and R. D. Singh, Agronomy Department, Rajendra Agricultural University (RAU), Bihar, Pusa (Samastipur) 848125, India

Due to availability of irrigation water in India's northern Bihar region, rice-based sequences of two or three crops a year have replaced the traditional rice monocrop. Irrigation water availability varies in the region.

We studied the performance of various cropping sequences under different water regimes. The experiment was conducted in a medium lowland site at the RAU Farm with five cropping sequences: rice - wheat - green gram, rice - winter maize - black gram, rice - potato - green gram, rice - Indian mustard - green gram, and rice - gram (chickpea) - green gram. Three levels of irrigation treatments were used in winter and summer seasons based on either irrigation water depth-cumulative pan evaporation ratio (IW:CPE) or days after sowing. Early rice variety Saket was transplanted on 20-25 Jul during 1986-91;

Table 2. Rice equivalence yield and net profit as influenced by irrigation levels and types of cropping sequences.^a Bihar, India. 1986-91.

Crop sequence	Level of irrigation					
	Suboptimal		Optimal		Supraoptimal	
	Yield (t/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)
Rice - wheat - green gram	7.9	343.4	8.2	360.7	8.7	377.6
Rice - winter maize - black gram	8.7	360.2	9.4	395.2	9.9	409.8
Rice - potato - green gram	12.6	409.9	14.5	519.2	15.2	544.1
Rice - Indian mustard - green gram	6.9	283.5	7.7	322.3	8.2	343.0
Rice - gram - green gram	7.0	290.9	7.4	306.8	7.6	315.7
	Yield		Net profit			
	SEM ±	CD (0.05)	SEM ±	CD (0.05)		
Irrigation (I) at same level of cropping sequence (C)	0.1	0.3	6.8	18.9		
C at same level of I	0.1	0.4	8.7	24.3		

^aAv of 6 yr.

irrigation water was kept at 7 cm 3 d after disappearance of ponded water.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with a combination of winter

and summer irrigation in the main plots and cropping sequence in the subplots, replicated three times. Irrigation schedules and amounts for each crop were

Table 1. Irrigation schedules and amounts for each crop of different sequences. Bihar, India. 1986-91.

Irrigation level	Wheat		Maize		Potato		Indian mustard		Gram		Green gram and black gram	
	Schedule (IW:CPE) ^a	Amount (cm)	Schedule (IW:CPE)	Amount (cm)	Schedule (IW:CPE)	Amount (cm)	Schedule (DAS) ^b	Amount (cm)	Schedule (DAS)	Amount (cm)	Schedule (DAS)	Amount (cm)
Suboptimal	0.5	12	0.5	18	0.6	12	Rainfed	0	Rainfed	0	Rainfed	0
Optimal	0.7	18	0.7	24	0.9	12	60	6	45	6	30	6
Supraoptimal	0.9	24	0.9	30	1.2	18	30, 60	12	45, 75	12	20, 40	12

^aIW:CPE = irrigation water depth - cumulative pan evaporation ratio. ^bDAS = days after sowing.

determined (Table 1). Optimum levels were based on regression lines developed at the site using 6-7 irrigation levels. (In a regression line, a point above optimum was termed supraoptimum; a point below, suboptimum.)

The soil is a sandy loam calcareous (23% CaCO₃) with pH of 8.4 (1:2 soil:water), developed from silty alluvium sediments with EC less than 0.6 dS/m. The water table was 2.0-6.1 m from the surface. Soil sampled from 0-30 cm contained 275 kg N/ha, 21.5 kg P/ha, and 83 kg K/ha.

Variation in irrigation levels and cropping sequences caused significant

differences in yield. The interaction between irrigation and cropping sequence was also significant. At each irrigation level, rice - potato - green gram yielded the most, followed by rice - winter maize - black gram. At the suboptimal and optimal levels, yields did not differ significantly between sequences containing mustard and gram. At the supraoptimal level, gram had a significant decrease in yield compared with mustard because gram does not respond to more frequent irrigation (Table 2).

Variation in net return due to irrigation level and cropping sequence was significant, as was the interaction effect

between irrigation and cropping sequence. Net return grew significantly with each increase in irrigation level for rice - potato - green gram, but for rice - winter maize - black gram, net return increased only up to the optimum irrigation level. Net returns were not significantly different between rice - wheat - green gram and rice - winter maize - black gram at the suboptimal level; at higher levels, net return was superior for the latter (Table 2). ■

Research methodology

An improved protocol for nonradioactive DNA analysis using digoxigenin labeling

R. Mauleon, R. Scott, and R. Nelson, IRRRI

We report here a simplified protocol for detecting membrane-bound DNA based on digoxigenin (DIG) labeling. DIG is a steroid which occurs naturally only in digitalis plants (*Digitaria lanata* and *D. purpurea*). The possibility of contaminating most biological samples with DIG-containing compounds is, therefore, minimal. In this procedure, the DIG-labeled DNA is hybridized to the target DNA. The labeled DNA hybrid is then detected in a two-step procedure, where an anti-DIG antibody conjugated to alkaline phosphatase is bound to the DIG-labeled probe. The physical location of the hybrids is then determined by using chromogenic or luminescent substrates for alkaline phosphatase.

DNA labeling

DIG is purchased as a labeled DNA precursor, DIG-11-dUTP (Boehringer Mannheim). This can be incorporated into a probe DNA by one of three methods: nick translation, random priming, or amplification using the polymerase chain reaction (PCR). Our random priming and PCR labeling procedures are described.

DNA labeling by random priming.

Probe DNA template is denatured for 10 min in a boiling water bath and chilled immediately on ice. The following are then added to every 10 µl of template (100 ng to 3 µg DNA): 2 µl of 10X primer mix (random hexanucleotides, 62.5 U/ml; Tris-HCl, 0.5 M (pH 7.2); MgCl₂, 0.1 M; dithioerythritol, 1 mM; and 2 mg/ml bovine serum albumin), 2 µl 10X dNTP mix (dATP, 1 mM; dCTP, 1 mM; dGTP, 1 mM; dTTP, 0.65 mM; and DIG-11-dUTP, 0.35 mM), 5 µl sterile distilled water, and 1 µl Klenow enzyme (2 U/µl). The resulting mixture is incubated for 2 h to overnight at 37 °C. The reaction is stopped by adding 2 µl of 0.2 M EDTA (pH 8). The labeled probe is precipitated by adding 10 µl of tRNA (2 mg/ml), 3.5 µl of 3 M sodium acetate, and 100 µl of cold absolute ethanol. The addition of tRNA is optional but beneficial if labeling a small amount of DNA. The labeled DNA is pelleted at 12,000 rpm for 5 min, rinsed with 70% ethanol, vacuum-dried, and resuspended in 200 µl TE-SDS (Tris-HCl, pH 8, 10 mM; EDTA, 1 mM; SDS, 0.1%). A fifth of the reaction is added to every 10-15 ml of hybridization buffer. The rest of the probe keeps indefinitely at 20 °C.

DNA labeling using PCR (adapted from a procedure from the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center).

A reaction mixture for thermal amplification is made with the following constituents: distilled water, 29.6 µl; 10X Taq incubation buffer (Tris-HCl, pH 8, 100 mM; MgCl₂, 15 mM; KCl, 500 mM; and gelatin, 1 mg/ml), 5 µl; 10X DIG-dNTP mix (dATP, dCTP, and dGTP, 2 mM each; dTTP, 1.65 mM; and DIG-dUTP, 0.35 mM), 5 µl; primer mix (1 µM each of M13-20 = 5'-GTAAAACGACGGCCAGT-3' and M13-R = 5'-AACAGCTATGACCATG-3'), 5 µl; Taq polymerase (5 U/µl), 0.4 µl; and template DNA (1 ng/µl), 5 µl. Thermal cycling is performed using the following program: 94 °C (1 min), 1 cycle; 94 °C (1 min), 55 °C (2 min), and 72 °C (1 min), 25 cycles; and 72 °C (1 min), 1 cycle. The amplified product is precipitated by adding 5 µl of 3 M sodium acetate and 100 µl of chilled absolute ethanol, rinsed with 70% ethanol, vacuum-dried, and resuspended in 50 µl of TE (Tri-HCl, pH 8, 10 mM; and EDTA, 1 mM). Typical yield is 2.5 µg. The M13 primers work for sequences cloned in pUC, pGEM, and pBluescript plasmids.

Hybridization and washing

The choice of blotting membrane is extremely important. We have had best results with positively charged nylon membrane (Hybond N⁺, Amersham). The